

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF TUTORIAL INSTITUTIONS ON THE COMPETENCE OF ACCOUNTING PROFESSIONALS**OGUNBEKUN Ayobami Oluwafemi**

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of tutorial institutions in the training of accountants in Nigeria. The researchers conducted this study in order to know from the students of accounting if there is need for a tutorial programme to enable them perform better in accounting examination and how the tutorial programmer can be better and if it has been working for them. For the purpose of this study, data were collected from non-tutorial students and tutorial institutions like PYE, MAYO and ICAN in order to obtain a reliable result. Questionnaire was the main instrument used in collecting the data; samples were selected through the use of simple random techniques. Two research questions and two hypotheses were developed and tested statistically using the Pearson moment correlation coefficient and the t-test statistics for the findings of the study revealed that: There is no correlation between tutorial institution and the training of accountants. There is significant difference between students that attend tutorial institutions and those that do not attend tutorial institutions. The effort of tutorial institutions in the training of accountant is 64% while the remaining 36% depends on other factor such as technological advancement etc. Based on these findings, conclusions were made and recommendations were put forward that tutorial institutions should ensure adequate planning and management control of the institution, all higher institutions of learning should have a list of accredited tutorial institutions and provide necessary advice to accounting students on the usefulness of these tutorial institutions, and the accounting curriculum should include courses offered in tutorial institutions as of the requirement.

Keywords: Accountancy, Curriculum, Tutorial Institutions, Training.**Introduction**

According to Adeniyi (2020), tutorial training centre is a type of educational approach where students receive personalized guidance, instruction and support from a tutor or instructor. Tutorial training is tailored to

individual needs, regular feedback and assessment, and involves one on one or small group instruction. Omolokun (2022) believed tutorial training assists the accounting students to gain a deeper understanding of complex topics, personalizes support and

guidance by helping to overcome challenges and achieve their goals, build confidence in their abilities, develop positive attitude towards learning and enhance accounting students to develop specific skills, such as problem solving, critical thinking and communication. Oshosaya (2021) emphasized that tutorial training provides a personalized and supportive learning environment that can help individual achieve their goals, develop new skills and apply accounting concepts and principles. Maurice (2022) explained that effective tutorial strategies in accounting comprise practical exercises and case studies which help accounting students apply theoretical knowledge to real accounting world. Tutorial training also provides regular feedback and assessment to accounting students to track the progress and identify areas for improvement and provides real world examples in practical application of accounting.

The few accountants we had in Nigeria before independence were not professionally qualified. With the growth in trade, commerce and industry in the early sixties, there was demand for the services of qualified accountants. People had to travel overseas to acquire Accounting Education since there was visually no higher institution and professional body undertaking Accounting Education. The first group of professionally qualified accountants emerged in Nigeria under the name: "The Association of Accountants in Nigeria". Government, in recognition of the importance of the accounting profession to national economy, created the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria in 1965 with the statutory responsibility of training accountants.

The Institute has been conducting standard examinations as well as absorbing accountants trained abroad after they had met certain requirements. This has resulted in the steady growth of the number of qualifying accountants every year. In the mid 1970s, various business organizations developed as a result of the favorable business climate in Nigeria, which was in turn due to the oil boom and the indigenization decrees. Consequent upon the increased number and complexity of business organizations and the uniqueness of the functions of accounting to any organization, there was a great demand for

the services of accountants. This is exemplified by the Center for Management Development Project of the country's demand for the production of one thousand accountants yearly in its bid to increase the number of professional Accountants in the economy adopted an accelerated programme (Maurice, 2022).

The aftermath of this was an appreciable increase in the yearly production of qualified accountants. Also, student registration increased phenomenally, especially at Higher National Diploma and University graduate levels. However, there is still a shortage of accountants in Nigeria's economy. The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN) was established by an act parliament on 1st September 1960 with the following power and responsibilities.

1. To determine what standard of knowledge and skill to be attained by persons seeking to become members of the accountancy profession and raising those standards from time to time as circumstance may permit.
2. To secure, in accordance with the provision of the act establishment and maintenance to register of fellows, associates and registered accountants entitled to practice as accountants and auditors and to publish from time to time a list of those persons.
3. To perform, through the council of the institute, all other functions conferred on it by the Act.

ICAN Journal (2022) identified two main classes of membership of the institute namely, Chartered Accountants and Registered Accountants. A chartered accountant is one who both passes qualifying examination for membership and completes the prescribed practical training, or holds a qualification granted outside Nigeria and for the time being is accepted by the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria and he satisfies the council of the institute that he has sufficient practical experience as an accountant. A registered accountant, for definitive purpose, is one who satisfies the council of the institute that immediately before the appointed day, he has not less than five years' experience as inspector and auditor of company affairs under the provision of the Companies Act.

As a result of the limitation on the incoming of chartered accountants in Nigeria by keen and competitive qualifying ICAN examination, an accounting tutorial institution can thus be described as a centre where the horizon of the students are broadened and where more attention is paid to details which may not have carried much weight in school. It could also be referred to as a place where up-coming accountants are trained and groomed basically for the purpose of writing and passing the professional qualifying accounting examination, that is ICAN. This study is therefore based on the statistical relationship between the past (that is the period before the inception of the accounting tutorial institution in Nigeria) and the present (referring to the period after the existence of the accounting tutorial institutions).

Scope of the study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effects which the establishment of various accounting tutorial institutions has on the training of accountants in Nigeria. As such, the researcher had to conduct an in-depth study into how two accounting tutorial institutions came about the motive behind their formation, their rate of growth over the years and how important they are in the accounting field. The researcher also had to examine a comparative study on the performance of their students in the ICAN examinations and finally made recommendations for improvement. Specifically, the study examined the quality of accountant's produced by these institutions, how encouraging their results and how Confident student are in them.

Significance of the study

Since the inception of accounting tutorial institution in Nigeria, there has been very little research work done in this area. The few publications available are not comprehensive in that, most of them are just researches and projectors to various types of allegations that they claim these tutorial centres try to portray to the public, for example, the claim by each of these tutorial centres among all these institutions, and also claims relating to leakages in examination questions. The Centres for Management Development

(C.M.D) has some relevance to the topic but apart from that there has been no specific published research work on successes in ICAN Examination and the development of accounting in Nigeria.

This study will therefore strive to put more light on the issues discussed above, as it was chosen amongst so many others because not chosen has been done in this area and as such, it is only a maiden research work to enlighten people on the effects these tutorial centers have on Accounting in Nigeria and above all how it has aided the development of the accounting profession.

Limitation of the study

The research was limited to the origin of accounting tutorial institutions in relation to the accounting examination body (ICAN). The effects tutorial institutions have on Accounting in Nigeria was also studied. As a result of financial and time constraints, it was impossible to cover the various Accounting tutorial institutions scattered all over the country. Therefore, the study was limited PYE Nigeria Limited and MAYO Associates Limited, both based in Lagos State. The analysis of this study was based on responses from the staff, students and ex-students of the tutorial institutions and also ICAN directors.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between tutorial institutions and growth in accounting professional?
2. What is the relationship between students that attend tutorial institution and students that do not?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between tutorial institutions and the training of accountants.
2. There is no significant difference between students that attend tutorial institutions and those that do not attend tutorial institutions.

Literature Review

The practice of accountancy in Nigeria could be traced from 1922 when the first companies' ordinance was enacted. Although there existed various record keeping forms before then, especially by churches and

intercontinental merchants who kept record of their trading in journal form, the legal basis for financial reporting was provided by the ordinance of 1922 (Omolokun, 2022). No significant development, however, existed in accounting education or any attempt made at institutionalizing the professions before 1960. Apart from the firm of Akintola Williams and Z.O. Oshosaya in (2021), major practicing firms of Accountants in Nigeria before independence were foreign based. Accounting education was done in Britain or through British based correspondence schools who coached for British Accounting qualification.

William and Co. (2021) submitted that the first attempt at producing accountants locally started in three colleges of Arts, Science and Technology located in Ibadan, Enugu and Zaria. This was designed to cater for the basic Science and Arts professional courses not provided by the only University in the Country then, the University College, Ibadan and only the Ibadan College of Art provided courses leading to the final certificate of ACCA. Others did not go beyond the intermediate stage.

Oshosanya (2021) stated that the process to institutionalize accounting profession (with mainly British qualification) was begun at a reception organized in honour of a visiting Treasurer of the Borough of Worthing (England) who was in the country in connection with the setting up of public libraries. It was here that the seed for the formation of the association of Nigerian accountants was sown in 1960. The association was the forerunner at the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria ICAN, which was incorporated by an act of parliament of 15 of 1965. Finally, it is worthy to mention that the first male chartered accountant in Nigeria is Mr. Akintola Williams and the first female graduate chartered accountant is Mrs. Bola Kuforiji Olubi.

ICAN: Its Role in Teaching of Professionals

The institute attaches considerable importance to the training of students who are required to acquire their practical experience in recognized training centers. Employment of accountants in the accounting or finance department of industrial or commercial undertaking, nationalized industries, etc. has to be approved by the council as possessing acceptable experience for this purpose. He has

to give precise nature of his work together with a certificate from his Chief Accountant (who has to be a member of the institute) in which it is stated that, during the course of his studentship he obtained the required experience (Kuforiji, 2020).

Adeniyi, (2020) stated that the period of practical experience needed for a candidate to be accomplished as an accountant depends on the relevance of his basic qualifications on registration. This is expected to be not less than 24 months and not more than 60 months. Adeniji (2020) also noted that the certificate to practice will be issued only to that candidate who has trained in a professional office and the minimum practical stated above have to be complete in the practicing office. ICAN, with proving examination syllabuses, gives students an idea on the sort of knowledge they need to acquire to be qualified. In other words, it specifies the areas of concentration required of students.

The institute therefore strives to bring together the professional and the intellectual skill components in the making of a chartered accountant and the final test of such skill is the examination conducted by the institute to examine the competence of such students.

The Origin of Accounting Tutorial Institution

According to A.J. Kay group (2020), they are recorded as the pioneer of accounting tutorial institutions. Quite a number of their students won the institution's prize for good performance. Professionals were recruited as lecturers on a full-time basis and they are highly dedicated to their duties and with the sound organizational structure of these institutions, they were successful in enrolling their trainee accountants in these institutions. In 1980s, at St. Jude Church, Ebute-Metta, an accounting tutorial institution existed but it was not run on a full scale commercial basis. The financial training center at Ojuelegba also started as a book selling center and lastly had the group organised at Railway Compound by Professor Adeyemo who also happened to be a past ICAN President. All these groups are no longer in existence.

The two accounting tutorial institutions in question, student PYE Nigeria Limited and MAYO Associate limited both originated in the 1980s. Student PYE Nigeria Limited was

founded in November 1986. Before this time, a group of qualified accountants who later formed the institution came up with the idea of providing for the use of students revision. This they did in 1968 not quite two weeks after the May Examination. The suggested solutions provided by these groups of accountants were already in circulation. With the success of these solutions, Kit Education Student PYE Nigeria Limited involved a highly integrated programme of lectures, private study tutorial guidance, written assignment, progress and revision tests.

MAYO Associate Limited, on the other hand, was incorporated in December 1984 by an exceptional team of tutors who had built their reputation at other accountancy colleges in the United Kingdom. This excellent team of tutors offered quality tuition and customer services to the students studying for the professional examination of the Institute of Chartered Accountant of Nigeria. Within a space of four years the company had achieved an enviable position of probably being the largest firm of tutors in the private sector with approximately 1500 trainee accountants successfully completing the course annually in the company (Hassan, 1996).

Objectives of the Tutorial Institution

The primary aim of student PYE Nigeria limited is to prepare students to satisfy the requirements of their participation examining body. Courses are designed to ensure that the syllabus is first carefully covered and fully revised before the examination. Another objective of the school is to provide support for policies designed to ensure the production of skilled professionals with potentials for high contribution quotient in government, commerce and industry. The achievement of this objective does not only require the provision of adequate lecturers but also the publication of professional text study manuals and workbooks to which they are committed. MAYO Associate Limited has basically same objectives. It aims to provide tuition of standard and quality which that obtain in England.

Mode of Operation

MAYO Associates Limited is operated on a commercial basis. The institution employs full time lecturers but courses are run mostly on a

part time basis except the full time five (5) week programme. The institution is none residential and everybody is given personal attention to ensure that students achieve an excellent result in their examination. Great emphasis is laid on four (4) areas that are vital to examination success namely,

1. An exception faculty of commercial tutors.
2. A carefully planned programme of study.
3. Up to date materials using the comprehensive MAYO BDP study text revision kits and tests.
4. Handout produced by those experienced in the use of computers.

The nucleus of MAYO Associates Limited is a team of experienced young men and women who have considerable expertise in teaching for the professional examination. These tutors are in a position to cover the complete range of subjects included in the ICAN syllabus to maintain a high pass rate and standard of service expected from such a well-known institutions. Student PYE Nigeria Limited, like MAYO Associates, also operates on a full-time basis, thus ensuring total commitment to their students. The institution claims that it is the only tuition house in Lagos with full-time lecturers (Kuforiji, 2020).

Organizational Structure

The two institutions, that is, student PYE Nigeria Limited and MAYO Associates are similar, are administered by the board of directors, which is headed by a board chairman. Other members of the board consist of an executive director and a manager. The running of these institutions is divided into two: the course division and publication division. The course division is basically in form of tuition, i.e. classroom based tuition used to prepare lecturers' time-table, fix lecture times and provides other materials needed in the classroom. The course administrators' assistant helps the course coordinator in discharging his duties and in seeing to it that his wishes were carried out. Olalere (2012) said the publication division consists of publication manager and publication officers.

Time/Period for Training

PYE Nigeria Limited and MAYO Associates Limited (2020) offer a comprehensive range of courses for students preparing for the May and November ICAN examination.

MAYO's Student's course lasts for 18 weeks and Student PYE's weekend intensive course also lasts for 10 weeks. It is a classroom-based programme of intensive lectures in all the subjects. Progress assignments and mock tests are administered to students. The syllabus for each level is exhaustively covered at least four (4) weeks to the relevant ICAN examination to give the students room for revision and orientation examination. Lecture session for the course takes place from 9:30am to 4:30pm between Monday and Friday.

The one year programme of MAYO Associates Limited is designed mainly for those who gradually prepare over almost a year before attempting their examination. This programme starts in July for MAY examination. Lecture period is from Monday through Friday 6:00pm-9:00pm. The last two programmes operated by MAYO Associates Limited are the MAYO Extended Programme (MEP) which is for the category of students who need a longer time than those in the standard course. This is for newly graduated students from the universities and polytechnics who require enough time to get acquitted with the fundamental elements and concepts of accounting to be able to get into the main stream of the ICAN syllabus. For this reason, the MEP involves a longer duration of

30 weeks. The programme however, extends to six week to the commencement of the examination to give students enough time for self-appraisal. MAYO Associates has successfully used the deficiencies identified by ICAN in the accelerated students.

Methodology

The discipline survey research design for this study is used to collect data from non-tutorial students, tutorial institutions (PYE & MAYO) and ICAN in order to get a reliable. The population used for this research includes males and females, age ranging from 20 years to 40 years. For this research, the samples used are students that did not attend tutorial institution between November 2000 and May 2005. The samples were selected through the use of simple random technique. Other features of the sample depend on Students PYE Nigeria limited and MAYO Associates, both in Lagos. Although other accounting tutorial institutions were considered, these two (2) were chosen.

The research instrument that was used is questionnaire. It was used to collect primary data for personal interview. Open and Close questions were set for the respondents so as to enable them to provide direct information. All questions were carefully ordered for easy understanding of questions drafted for the respondents. This is to ensure the validity and reliability of the intended responses. More so, efforts were made to ensure the consistency of the responses.

Presentation and Analysis of Data**Table 1: Presentation of Data**

ICAN	20	9	14	19	18	3	11	13	19	15
Tutorial	20	12	19	30	28	5	24	13	22	19
Non-Tutorial (%)	10	5	17	18	19	2	10	7	15	13

Hypothesis: There is no correlation between students that attended normal institutions and the training of accountant.

Hi: There is correlation between students that attended tutorial institutions and the training of Accountants.

In an attempt to determine whether there is correlation between students that attend tutorial institution and the training of accountants, secondary data was generated from PYE, MAYO and

ICAN and they were analyzed in the Table II below, using Pearson monument correlation coefficient. The procedure is to state the hypothesis and follow it with the corresponding table.

Table II; Correlation Coefficient Based on Secondary Data

N	EX	EY	EX ²	EY ²	EXY	R	R ²	x	Df	t cal	t tab	Decision
10	192	1412	4202	2,247	2,999	0.8	0.64	0.05	8	6.29	2.306	Accept Hi Reject Ho

The finding from the correlation coefficient of determination obtained in the above table indicates that 64% of the level of training accountants depends on tutorial institutions, while the remaining 36% depends on other factors. More so, the decision is to accept alternatives hypothesis (i.e. Hi), there is correlation between tutorial institutions and the training of accountants.

Hypothesis 2;

HO; There is no significant difference between students that attend tutorial institutions and students that do not attend tutorial institutions.

Hi;- There is a significant difference between students that attend Tutorial Institutions and students that do not attend tutorial institutions.

In an attempt to determine whether there is a significant difference or not between students that attend tutorial institutions and students who do not attend tutorial institution, the responses of students that do not attend tutorial institutions in the questionnaire and the secondary data collected from PYE and MAYO were analyzed in the Table III below using students T-test methods.

Table III; T-Test Based on Both Primary and Secondary Data

Data	X	N	X	SD	DF	α	TCAL	TTAB	DECISION
SECONDARY	192	10	19.2	7.58					Accept Hi
PRIMARY	116	10	11.6	5.78	18	0.05	6.58	1.734	Reject Ho

The observed differences in the mean score are statistically significant at 0.05 level. This was shown above in which the t-calculated is greater than the t-tabulated, which shows that the alternative hypothesis (i.e. Hi,) is accepted, that is, there is a significant difference between students that attend tutorial institutions and students that do not attend tutorial Institutions.

Summary of Findings

The following are the findings of the study:

- There is correlation between tutorial institutions and the training of accountants.
- The effect of tutorial institutions in the training of accountants is 64% while

the remaining 36% depends on other factors such as Technological advancement etc.

- There is significant difference between students that attend tutorial institutions and students that do not attend tutorial institutions.

Discussion of Findings

From the result of the analyzed data, it is evident that there is correlation between the effect of tutorial institutions and the training of accountants. More so, the effect of tutorial institutions in the training of accountants is 64%, while the remaining 36% depends on other factors such as Technological environment etc. Furthermore, the study

reveals that there is a significant difference between students that attend tutorial institutions. In one of the ICAN students' Journals, the list of ICAN accredited centers was included, invariably, showing that ICAN itself supports the existence of tutorial institutions, because they know it affects the training of accountants positively. In summary, tutorial institutions should be encouraged in Nigeria towards the training and development of accountant.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Tutorial institutions should be encouraged and adequate planning, provisions and control should be given to the management of tutorial institutions.
2. Tutorial institutions are still very much under-developed in terms of facilities, practically, technological development, exposure, awareness, etc., so, government should assist in the development of tutorial institutions by providing necessary infrastructural facilities to aid the development of tutorial institutions.
3. Because it enhances the growth of tutorial institutions, all higher institutions should also have the list of the accredited tutorial institutions and provide necessary advice on existence of tutorial institutions.
4. Accounting curriculum should include courses offered in tutorial institutions.

Conclusion

It is hoped that the existence, growth and development of tutorial institutions in Nigeria will help to increase the training and development of accountants in the country both locally and internationally. There is need for enlightenment programme among the undergraduate students to draw their attention to the effect of tutorial institutions in the training of accountants.

As we fast approach the period of globalization and technological advancement, the university curriculum cannot only train accountants to meet the challenges, so the support of tutorial institutions is adequately

needed. Although the findings of this study cannot be taken as the ultimate conclusion, nevertheless, they form the basis for further research study.

References

- Adeniyi (2020) *"Qualifications as an Accountant"* Lexy Press Ltd. Ikeja, Lagos.
- Centre for Management Development (1967) *"100 yearly research work"* University Press Ltd.
- ICAN (1965) *"Act of parliament of 15 of 1965"*
- ICAN (1999) *"Rules of Professional conduct of members"* in members Handbook
- ICAN Student Journal (2021) *The relationship between Tutorial Institutions and the development of Accountant* Vol. I
- ICAN students Journal (2021) *"The role of Tutorial Institutions in the development of Accountant"* Vol II
- K. Ngwanu, X. Yaba, N. Ngobese, (2022) Durban University of Technology (South Africa) *(Investigation into the tutorial programme effects an student results in the Faculty of Accounting and Information)*.
- Maurice, Jack (2021) *"Why Tutorial Institutions in the development of Accountant"* New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- MAYO (2020) *"Registered Students Records"*
- Omolokun I.O. (2022) *"Ordinance of Financial Reporting 4th Dimension Publication Ltd"*.
- Oshika J.O. (2022) *"Research Methodology"* Adeola Press Ltd Ibadan
- Oshosanya (2021) *"The Development of Accountancy Profession"* Top speed Press, Ilorin Kwara State.
- PYE (2005) *"Registered Students Records"*

